

The management of pediatric status epilepticus: protocol for a systematic review of clinical practice guidelines

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) results from either the failure of mechanisms responsible for seizure termination or the initiation of mechanisms leading to abnormally prolonged seizures.¹

With an incidence ranging from 3 to 73 episodes per 100.000 children per year, SE is the most common neurological emergency in pediatrics.^{2,3} Given its potential to cause neuronal death and network disruption,

leading to a range of neurological, cognitive, and behavioural sequelae, as well as increased mortality, SE is considered a highly time-sensitive emergency.⁴⁻⁷

Despite the well-documented detrimental effects of delayed treatment on seizure termination and clinical outcomes, both pre-hospital and in-hospital management of SE is often untimely in real-world settings.⁸⁻¹¹ Moreover, several studies report a gap between clinical practice guidelines (CPGs)-based management and actual clinical practice.¹²⁻¹⁵

CPGs are “statements that include recommendations, intended to optimize patient care, that are informed by a systematic review of evidence and an assessment of the benefits and harms of alternative care options”.¹⁶ The quality of CPGs may influence acceptance, adherence and confidence among end-users. Various domains define CPGs quality, including scope and purpose, stakeholder involvement, rigour of development, clarity and presentation, applicability, editorial independence. Among these, applicability may often be neglected, despite being crucial to enhance CPGs adherence by providing users with tools for clinical implementation (e.g. resource considerations, instructions, summary documents, checklists, algorithms).¹⁷⁻¹⁹

Low adherence to SE-CPGs may lead to the overuse of benzodiazepines, uncertainty regarding timing of treatment and failure to escalate therapy when required. Therefore, improving adherence to CPGs is likely a key factor in overcoming treatment-related barriers to care for SE and improving outcomes.¹⁴ A systematic review of adult SE-CPGs identified several quality flaws that could hinder adherence to CPGs, potentially contributing to the gap between guideline-based SE management and actual clinical practice.²⁰ No comparable critical assessment of pediatric SE-CPGs has yet been conducted. Such an appraisal may support the development of tools to facilitate the clinical implementation of CPGs (e.g., simplified algorithms or educational materials for healthcare professionals) ultimately promoting greater adherence to guidelines.

Objective

The purpose of this protocol is to report the rationale and methodology for a systematic review of the available CPGs about the diagnostic and therapeutic management of pediatric SE. The aim of the systematic review will be: (1) to assess the quality of CPGs, with particular emphasis to their applicability; (2) to highlight different recommendations between CPGs; (3) to suggest possible research gaps to be addressed in this field.

Methods

This protocol is following the methodology suggested by Johnston et al.²¹ and is registered with PROSPERO database and published on the Zenodo repository and on Researchgate. The Italian Pediatric Status Epilepticus (IPSE) Group (<https://ipsegroup.it/>) supports this study.

Eligibility criteria

The analysis will be performed on CPGs that include recommendations on the diagnostic and therapeutic management of SE specifically in the pediatric population, excluding newborns (1 month to 17 years). Guidelines that do not provide recommendations explicitly for the pediatric population will be excluded.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined according to the PICAR framework for systematic reviews of CPGs (Table 1).²¹ To ensure clinical relevance and methodological quality, eligibility will be limited to the most recent versions of CPGs issued by major national or international health authorities, professional organizations, or scientific societies. Only CPGs published from 2015 onwards will be considered, as this marks the publication of the operational definition of SE, which represents a paradigm shift in the classification and methodological approach to SE.¹ No restrictions will be applied regarding sex, ethnicity, or setting. Guidelines will be considered if available in English, French, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, German, Dutch, Swedish, Danish, Norwegian, Finnish, Polish. The following clinical subgroups will be outlined: convulsive SE (CSE); SE without prominent motor phenomena (“non-convulsive SE” – NCSE); other SE (e.g. SE with other prominent motor features, refractory SE). The interventions of interest will be procedures/tests to diagnose SE and its etiology (neurophysiology, neuroradiology and laboratory procedures), as well as treatments (excluding etiologic treatment). The management will be framed, if appropriate and possible, by the duration of SE and setting (pre-hospital, hospital).

Data sources and searches

We will search Medline (PubMed) and EMBASE databases (see Appendix for applied search strategies), guideline registries, EBM databases, point-of-care tools, websites of governmental organisations, websites of international neurologic societies (see list in Appendix). Eventually, we will search Google for additional unique records using broader search terms for “pediatric status epilepticus” and “guideline”, shifting through the first 100 results, and scan the reference lists of all retrieved CPGs.

Study selection and data extraction

Two researchers (LB and KD) will independently screen the titles and abstracts of the identified records for eligibility. Full text will be retrieved for those records that appear to meet the inclusion criteria. The full text will be checked for eligibility by two researchers (LB and KD) independently. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion. Any associated companion article (e.g. methodology supplements and background documents) or relevant accompanying online information will also be retrieved for each included CPG, as well as document metadata (title, year, country of origin, authors, funding source, CPG development method, quality grading system). Two researchers (LB, KD) will extract the text of the recommendations of interest. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion.

Quality assessment

Three researchers (LB, KD, LV) will independently evaluate the quality of the CPG using the AGREE II tool (Brouwers et al., 2010), which assesses 23 items across six domains: scope and purpose, stakeholder involvement, rigour of development, clarity of presentation, applicability and editorial independence. Each item will be rated on a 7-point Likert-type scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Following the AGREE II user’s manual, a final quality score will be calculated for each domain and expressed as a

percentage. A CPG will be classified as “high quality” in case it achieves a score above 70% in all domains, as recommended in the manual.

Data synthesis and analysis

We will report the main characteristics of the included CPGs in an Excel table, including the AGREE II scores for each CPG, individual domain and overall domain. Based on the scores of individual domains, we will identify factors contributing to lower guideline quality. To systematically compare, categorize, and summarize the nature of recommendations across and within indications, we will develop a recommendation matrix. The quality of evidence supporting these recommendations will be assessed. The rating systems of all CPGs will be reviewed and compared with each other to facilitate a direct comparison of the quality of evidence between recommendations reported by different CPGs. We will consider recommendations related to the diagnostic and therapeutic management of SE, calculating the proportion of CPGs that cover the different types of indications. We will use thematic analysis²² to identify common themes among the recommendations, using each recommendation matrix to facilitate the process. First, recommendations and their thematic codes will be aligned side-by-side. Then, one reviewer will read and re-read each recommendation and its associated code to gain familiarity with the data. The reviewer will then revisit and refine the codes using an iterative process as new ideas emerge. Once completed, the revised set of codes will be examined to identify broader themes. Another reviewer will independently assess and challenge these themes, and the final set will be established through consensus.

Table 1. PICAR inclusion criteria (Johnston et al., 2019)²¹.

<p>POPULATION, CLINICAL INDICATION AND CONDITION(S)</p>	<p>Patients aged 1 month to 17 years with SE, in any clinical setting (out of hospital; ER; hospital; ICUs)</p> <p>The following clinical conditions will be outlined: CSE, NCSE, other SE</p>
<p>INTERVENTIONS</p>	<p>Any diagnostic management</p> <p>Any therapeutic management</p>
<p>COMPARATOR(S), COMPARISON(S), AND (KEY) CONTENT</p>	<p>All comparators and comparisons are of interest</p> <p>Key contents: the following elements will be outlined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - procedures/tests on diagnosis of etiology (blood tests, neuroradiology) - procedures/test on diagnosis of SE (EEG) - treatment of SE (etiologic treatment will be excluded)

	These elements will be framed, if appropriate and possible, according to SE semeiology (CSE, NCSE, other SE), setting (pre-hospital, hospital), response to therapy (RSE).
ATTRIBUTES OF ELIGIBLE CPGs	<p>Publishing body: national health authorities and national or international professional organisations or societies</p> <p>Language: English, French, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, German, Dutch, Swedish, Danish, Norwegian, Finnish, Polish</p> <p>Year of publication: 2015-present</p> <p>System of rating evidence: Any</p> <p>Scope: Must contain recommendations on diagnosis and / or treatment of SE</p> <p>Recommendations: At least one eligible recommendation reported</p>
RECOMMENDATION CHARACTERISTICS	<p>Levels of confidence: No restrictions</p> <p>Locating recommendations: Within CPG text, tables, algorithms or decision paths</p>

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Appendix – Search strategy

PUBMED

Search terms will be as follows:

SEARCH	QUERY
1	"Epileptic status"[Title/Abstract:~4] OR "Epilepticus status"[Title/Abstract:~4] OR "Epilepsy status"[Title/Abstract:~4] OR "CSE"[Title/Abstract] OR "NCSE"[Title/Abstract] OR "RSE"[Title/Abstract] OR "Status Epilepticus"[Mesh]
2	infanc*[Title/Abstract] OR infant*[Title/Abstract] OR child*[Title/Abstract] OR pediatric*[Title/Abstract] OR paediatric*[Title/Abstract] OR Youth*[Title/Abstract] OR Teen*[Title/Abstract] OR ("Adolescent"[Mesh] OR "Child"[Mesh] OR "Infant"[Mesh])
3	1 AND 2
4	"guideline"[Publication Type] OR "practice guideline"[Publication Type] OR guideline*[Title/abstract] OR guidance*[Title] OR recommendation*[Title]
5	4 AND 3
6	5 AND Publication date from 2010 to 2025

EMBASE

Search terms will be as follows:

SEARCH	QUERY
1	'epileptic state'/exp
2	cse:ti,ab,kw OR ncse:ti,ab,kw OR rse:ti,ab,kw OR ((epilep* NEAR/4 (status OR state)):ti,ab,kw)
3	1 OR 2
4	3 AND ([adolescent]/lim OR [child]/lim [infant]/lim OR [newborn]/lim OR [preschool]/lim OR [school]/lim)
5	.'practice guideline'/exp
6	recommendation*: ti OR guidance*:ti OR guideline*:ab,ti
7	5 OR 6
8	4 AND 7
9	8 AND [2010-2025]/py
10	9 AND ('article'/it OR 'article in press'/it)
11	10 AND [embase]/lim NOT ([embase]/lim AND [medline]/lim)

Guideline registries, EBM databases, point-of-care tools

Search terms: *epilepsy, status epilepticus, convulsion, child*, pediatric*, guideline* recommendation**

Catalogage et l'Indexation des Sites Médicaux de langue Française (CISMeF):

<https://www.cismef.org/cismef/>

DynaMed: <https://www.dynamed.com/>

ECRI Guidelines Trust: <https://guidelines.ecri.org/>

Guidelinecentral: <https://www.guidelinecentral.com/guidelines/>

International Guidelines Library, Guidelines International Network (GIN): <https://g-i-n.net/international-guidelines-library/>

Red Española de Agencias de Evaluación de Tecnologías Sanitarias y Prestaciones del Sistema Nacional de Salud: <https://redets.sanidad.gob.es/>

Tripdatabase Trip Medical database: <https://www.tripdatabase.com/>

WHO: <https://www.who.int/publications/who-guidelines>

Governmental organisations

Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network SIGN: <https://www.sign.ac.uk/>

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence NICE: <https://www.nice.org.uk/>

SNLG: <https://www.iss.it/snlg-copertina>

Haute Autorité de Santé HAS: https://www.has-sante.fr/jcms/c_431294/en/clinical-practice-guidelines-cpg

Cadth: <https://www.cda-amc.ca/find-reports>

International scientific societies

Pediatric neurology

- African Child Neurology Association (ACNA) - <https://www.icnapedia.org/my-groups/60-acna/timeline>
- Asian and Oceanian Child Neurology Association (AOCNA) - <https://www.aocna.org/>
- Brazilian Society of Pediatric Neurology (Sociedade Brasileira de Neurologia Infantil - SBNI)
- British Paediatric Neurology Association (BPNA) - <https://bpna.org.uk/>
- Child Neurology Society - <https://www.childneurologysociety.org/>
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Neuropädiatrie (GNP) - <https://gesellschaft-fuer-neuropaediatrie.org/>
- European Paediatric Neurology Society (EPNS) - <https://www.epns.info/>
- International Child Neurology Association (ICNA) - <https://icnapedia.org/>
- Japanese Society of Child Neurology - <https://www.childneuro.jp/en/6449/>
- Latin American Society of Pediatric Neurology (LANSPN / SLANP)
- Paediatric Neurology and Development Association of Southern Africa (PANDA-SA) - <https://www.pandasa.org/web/index.asp>
- Sociedad Española de Neurología Pediátrica (SENEP) - <https://www.senep.es/>
- Società Italiana di Neurologia Pediatrica (SINP) - <https://neurologiapediatria.it/>
- Società Italiana di Neuropsichiatria dell'Infanzia e dell'Adolescenza (SINPIA) - <https://sinpia.eu/>

- Société Européenne de Neurologie Pédiatrique (SENP+) - <https://senp-neuropediatrie.eu/fr/page-daccueil/>

Epilepsy

- American Epilepsy Society - <https://www.aesnet.org/about/position-statements>
- Canadian League Against Epilepsy (CLAE-LCCE) - <https://claegroup.org/>
- Chinese Association Against Epilepsy (CAAE) - <https://www.caae.org.cn/>
- Dansk Epilepsi Selskab - <https://www.epilepsiforeningen.dk/>
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Epileptologie (DGfE) - <https://www.dgfe.org/>
- Epilepsia de Chile - <https://www.epilepsiadechile.com/>
- International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) - <https://www.ilae.org/guidelines>
- Japanese Epilepsy Society (JES) - <https://jes-jp.org/jes/en/index.html>
- Latin American Epilepsy Society (LACE / LALE)
- Lega Italiana Contro l’Epilessia (LICE) - <https://lice.it/>
- Liga Argentina Contro la Epilepsia (LACE) - <https://www.lace.org.ar/>
- Liga Brasileira de Epilepsia (LBE) - <https://www.epilepsia.org.br/>
- Mexican League Against Epilepsy - <https://camelice.org/>
- Nederlandse Liga tegen Epilepsie - <https://epilepsieliga.nl/>
- Norsk Epilepsiselskap - <https://www.epilepsi.no/>
- Polskie Towarzystwo Epileptologii (PTE) - <https://www.epileptologia.pl/>
- Suomen Epilepsiaseura - <https://www.epilepsia.fi/>
- Svenska Epilepsisällskapet - <https://www.epilepsisallskapet.se/>

Paediatric emergency medicine and intensive care

- Advanced Life Support Group (ALSG) - EPALS (European Paediatric Advanced Life Support) - <https://www.alsg.org/home/>
- American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) - Section on Emergency Medicine (SOEM) - <https://www.aap.org/en/community/aap-sections/emergency-medicine/>
- American College of Emergency Physicians (ACEP) - Pediatric Section - <https://www.acep.org/pediatrics>
- Asian Society for Pediatric Emergency Medicine (ASPEM) - <https://www.asiansem.org/>
- Australasian College for Emergency Medicine (ACEM) - Paediatric Emergency Section - <https://acem.org.au/>
- Canadian Association of Emergency Physicians (CAEP) – Pediatric Emergency Medicine Section - <https://caep.ca/em-community/pediatric-emergency-medicine-section>
- Canadian Paediatric Society - <https://cps.ca/>

- Deutsche Interdisziplinäre Vereinigung für Intensiv- und Notfallmedizin (DIVI) - <https://www.divi.de/>
- European Society for Emergency Medicine (EUSEM) - Pediatric Section - <https://eusem.org/>
- Indian Academy of Pediatrics (IAP) - <https://www.iapindia.org/>
- International Federation for Emergency Medicine (IFEM) - <https://www.ifem.cc/>
- International Liaison Committee on Resuscitation (ILCOR) - <https://www.ilcor.org/>
- Latin American Society of Pediatric Emergency Medicine (SLEPE)
- Neurocritical Care Society - <https://www.neurocriticalcare.org/>
- Pediatric Emergency Care Applied Research Network (PECARN) - <https://pecarn.org/>
- Resuscitation Council UK - <https://www.resus.org.uk/>
- Royal College of Paediatrics and Child Health (RCPCH) - Emergency Medicine Group (UK) - <https://www.rcpch.ac.uk/>
- Società Italiana di Medicina di Emergenza e Urgenza Pediatrica (SIMEUP) - <https://simeup.it/>
- World Federation of Pediatric Intensive and Critical Care Societies (WFPICCS) - <https://wfpiccs.org/>
- Accademia Medica Infermieristica di Emergenza e Terapia Intensiva Pediatrica (AMIETIP) - <https://amietip.it/>
- Società di Anestesia e Rianimazione Neonatale Pediatrica Italiana (SARNEPI) - <https://www.sarnepi.it>

Google

Search terms: *epilepsy, status epilepticus, convulsion, child*, pediatric*, guideline* recommendation**. Their translation in French, Spanish, Italian.

Screening of the first 100 results.